

Medical Out-of-Distribution Analysis Challenge 25: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Medical Out-of-Distribution Analysis Challenge 25

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

MOOD 25

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Despite advancements in biomedical image computing, creating annotated training datasets remains a costly and time-intensive process, requiring the expertise of domain specialists. This dependency on labeled data limits scalability, particularly when dealing with new imaging modalities, evolving parameters, or shifting patient demographics. Moreover, standard algorithms often fail when faced with out-of-distribution (OOD) samples, resulting in inaccurate or overconfident predictions [20–23]. Even clinicians can overlook unexpected findings in medical images, a phenomenon known as "inattentive blindness" [1].

Unsupervised and weakly supervised anomaly detection presents a promising alternative, as it does not require labeled datasets and can generalize to previously unseen pathologies. This approach streamlines model adaptation to new imaging modalities and directs physicians' attention to overlooked abnormalities, potentially improving diagnostic accuracy. While anomaly detection has been a topic of active research [8–17], particularly in the medical domain [4–7], the field lacks a standardized benchmark for fair algorithm comparison in medical and radiological image analysis [2, 3].

To address this gap, we propose the Medical Out-of-Distribution (MOOD) Challenge, offering a benchmark and dataset for anomaly detection.

Insights from previous iterations of the challenge (MOOD 2020–2024) [25] revealed that while some methods performed well in specific cases, they often struggled with clinically significant anomalies [6, 18–19, 23]. To address this, we have broadened the scope to include more clinically relevant and synthetic examples. These updates have demonstrated improved performance for certain medical conditions, showcasing the potential of anomaly detection approaches. However, significant challenges remain in achieving clinical applicability, emphasizing the need for continued innovation.

We have transitioned to an object-centric metric for pixel-wise evaluation to better align with medical objectives [9, 26]. This shift incorporates insights from real-world evaluations and feedback from clinical partners. For the next year, we will continue refining our synthetic anomalies to create a more robust and representative challenge. Additionally, we are introducing a new "real-world" use-case task focused on anomaly detection.

Starting in 2026, the MOOD Challenge will adopt a rotating leadership structure, with the University of Erlangen, Imperial College London, TU Munich, and DKFZ taking turns as the primary organizers each year. Each institution will bring unique datasets and medical objectives, reflecting diverse perspectives on out-of-distribution detection and anomaly localization while staying true to the MOOD spirit.

The MOOD Challenge is dedicated to driving methodological advancements in anomaly detection while benchmarking their effectiveness. It addresses critical challenges in medical image analysis, including limited labeled data and out-of-distribution errors.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Anomaly detection, Anomaly localization, Out-of-distribution detection, novelty detection

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The MOOD Challenge stands as the first—and currently the only—benchmark dedicated to anomaly localization and out-of-distribution (OOD) detection in medical imaging. While previous editions have highlighted the potential of existing methodologies and provided a valuable snapshot of the field's progress, they also underscored that these challenges remain far from solved. Significant gaps persist, offering ample opportunity for further advancements.

This year, besides providing a completely new test-set for the first two tasks, the Challenge introduces a groundbreaking addition: a real "open-world" dataset tailored to a clinical use case. This new dataset shifts the focus from purely methodological benchmarking to clinical applicability, evaluating algorithms on their ability to detect rare and highly varied conditions in brain images. By bridging the gap between academic research and real-world medical challenges, this novel task aims to drive the development of approaches that are not only methodologically robust but also clinically impactful.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

1. Image-Level (Scan-Level) Out-of-Distribution (OOD) Detection

Task Description:

This task focuses on identifying entire medical scans (e.g., MRI or CT) that contain anomalies or conditions not present in the training data. The goal is to determine whether a scan is "in-distribution" (normal or within expected variability) or "out-of-distribution" (containing unexpected anomalies or pathologies).

Application Scenarios:

Triage Systems: Prioritize scans with potential anomalies for further review by radiologists or automated diagnostic systems.

Clinical Workflows: Assist in managing large volumes of medical imaging data by flagging scans requiring detailed analysis.

Research and Development: Evaluate the robustness of models in handling unseen pathologies or variations introduced by new imaging modalities or patient demographics.

2. Object-Level Anomaly Detection

Task Description:

This task aims to localize specific regions within medical images that exhibit abnormal patterns or anomalies. The challenge lies in accurately identifying and delineating these regions, particularly when they are small or subtle.

Application Scenarios:

Guiding Radiologist Attention: Highlight regions of interest in images to reduce oversight and improve diagnostic accuracy.

Preoperative Planning: Identify critical abnormalities for surgical or interventional planning.

3. Real-World "Open-World" Anomaly Detection

Task Description:

This task evaluates algorithms on a real-world dataset with diverse and rare medical conditions in brain images. The goal is to detect anomalies across a broad range of pathology types, simulating the variability encountered in clinical practice.

Application Scenarios:

Rare Disease Diagnosis: Support the detection of rare and poorly understood conditions that may otherwise be overlooked.

General Clinical Applicability: Test the adaptability of algorithms to handle diverse anomalies and ensure performance in real-world medical scenarios.

Robust Anomaly Detection Models: Benchmark algorithms in a clinically relevant environment, encouraging the development of methods that generalize beyond synthetic or narrowly defined datasets.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

No Workshop.

But we want to note that the MICCAI challenge event is planned for a 2-hour slot. We plan a publication of the results after the challenge. In previous years, we published a challenge report in IEEE TMI and offered participants to publish their results as Springer proceedings. If the progress of the algorithms this year is extraordinary, we aim for MIA or TMI to publish a dedicated challenge report paper, and, given enough interest from the participants, plan to organize a proceedings issue (either from Springer or Melba), where the participants can publish a short paper about their works.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

10 per task (based on the previous years)

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

In previous years, we published a challenge report in IEEE TMI and offered participants to publish their results as Springer proceedings. If the progress of the algorithms this year is extraordinary, we aim for MIA or TMI to publish a dedicated challenge report paper, and, given enough interest from the participants, plan to organize a proceedings issue (either from Springer or Melba), where the participants can publish a short paper about their works.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

We plan on using the Synapse platform for the submission of docker files for testing. We will run a continuous evaluation pipeline after the challenge starts where participants can check if their submission is valid and their toy task scores.

TASK 1: Image-Level

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

A core challenge in medical image analysis is the reliance on large, annotated datasets, which hinders adaptability to new pathologies, changes in imaging parameters, or diverse patient demographics. This sample-level task focuses on out-of-distribution (OOD) detection, where participants will develop algorithms capable of identifying medical images (e.g., brain MRI, abdominal CT) that contain:

Clinically relevant abnormalities or conditions: Samples with pathologies not present in the training data.

Unexpected variations: Images reflecting shifts in modalities, protocols, or patient populations.

Corrupted samples: Images containing artifacts or errors that could compromise analysis.

This task simulates real-world scenarios where medical professionals encounter unexpected findings or technical image quality issues. Success in this task translates to anomaly detection methods that can:

Prioritize Patients: Flag images that potentially contain pathologies requiring further examination or urgent attention.

Streamline Model Adaptation: Detect images requiring model updates or retraining.

Address Limited Labeled Data: Advance anomaly detection to function effectively even when comprehensive labeling is infeasible or impossible.

Enhance Data Quality: Improve robustness by identifying corrupted samples that could negatively impact downstream tasks.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

N/A

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

David Zimmerer, Gregor Köhler, Peter Full, Klaus Maier-Hein

Div. Medical Image Computing (MIC), German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)

Annika Reinke, Lena Maier-Hein

Div Computer Assisted Medical Interventions (CAMI), German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

David Zimmerer (MIC, DKFZ) d.zimmerer@dkfz.de

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://synapse.org/mood>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

No prizes have yet been determined. Currently, the winner will win the right to brag about the results.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

By default (i.e. if they don't decline) the top 3 (winning) teams will be announced publicly. The remaining teams may decide if they choose to appear on the public Leaderboard.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participating teams with a valid submission. Teams that reveal their identity, can nominate members of their team as co-authors for the challenge paper (as many members as the team wants). However, we reserve the right to exclude teams and team members if they do not adhere to the challenge rules and guidelines.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/mood>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Teams are allowed three submissions per challenge task, however, only the latest submission will be considered. For each challenge submission, the teams will receive the results on a very simple "toy" test-case, which will not be included in the final testset. We also already made the "toy" case and testing script publicly available so that the participants can check beforehand if their submission won't cause any errors and to compare the reported results with their own to check for any additional occurring errors. Additionally, a dedicated toy-case evaluation queue will be available where participants can submit their solutions to our cluster and only run the toy cases and receive toy-case results. This toy-case evaluation queue will not count as a challenge submission, will have no submission limit, and only serve as a "will run successfully" check.

We may offer rankings only (no scores) on a toy subset of the test set to give participants some directional feedback.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)

- the release date(s) of the results

Release of training cases: 15 March 2025

Registration Until: 15 August 2025

Submission of Dockers: 16 August 2025

Invitation of the participants to present their results: 1 September 2025

Release date of the results: MICCAI 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The provided challenge data is anonymized.

According to [Euro2016], the anonymized data can be used for the challenge.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

For the Brain Data the following Licence applies: "I will not attempt to establish the identity of or attempt to contact any of the included human subjects. I understand that under no circumstances will the code that would link these data to Protected Health Information be given to me, nor will any additional information about individual human subjects be released to me under these Open Access Data Use Terms. I will comply with all relevant rules and regulations imposed by my institution. This may mean that I need my research to be approved or declared exempt by a committee that oversees research on human subjects, e.g. my IRB or Ethics Committee. The released HCP data are not considered de-identified, insofar as certain combinations of HCP Restricted Data (available through a separate process) might allow identification of individuals. Different committees operate under different national, state and local laws and may interpret regulations differently, so it is important to ask about this. If needed and upon request, the HCP will provide a certificate stating that you have accepted the HCP Open Access Data Use Terms. I may redistribute original WU-Minn HCP Open Access data and any derived data as long as the data are redistributed under these same Data Use Terms. I will acknowledge the use of WU-Minn HCP data and data derived from WU-Minn HCP data when publicly presenting any results or algorithms that benefitted from their use. Papers, book chapters, books, posters, oral presentations, and all other printed and digital presentations of results derived from HCP data should contain the following wording in the acknowledgments section: "Data were provided [in part] by the Human Connectome Project, WU-Minn Consortium (Principal

Investigators: David Van Essen and Kamil Ugurbil; 1U54MH091657) funded by the 16 NIH Institutes and Centers that support the NIH Blueprint for Neuroscience Research; and by the McDonnell Center for Systems Neuroscience at Washington University."Authors of publications or presentations using WU-Minn HCP data should cite relevant publications describing the methods used by the HCP to acquire and process the data. The specific publications that are appropriate to cite in any given study will depend on what HCP data were used and for what purposes. An annotated and appropriately up-to-date list of publications that may warrant consideration is available at <http://www.humanconnectome.org/about/acknowledgehcp.html>The WU-Minn HCP Consortium as a whole should not be included as an author of publications or presentations if this authorship would be based solely on the use of WU-Minn HCP data.Failure to abide by these guidelines will result in termination of my privileges to access WU-Minn HCP data."For the Abdominal data the following Licence applies:"Citations & Data Usage PolicyThis collection is freely available to browse, download, and use for commercial, scientific and educational purposes as outlined in the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License. See TCIA's Data Usage Policies and Restrictions for additional details. Questions may be directed to help@cancerimagingarchive.net.Please be sure to include the following citations in your work if you use this data set: Data CitationSmith K, Clark K, Bennett W, Nolan T, Kirby J, Wolfsberger M, Moulton J, Vendt B, Freymann J. (2015). Data From CT_COLONOGRAPHY. The Cancer Imaging Archive. <http://doi.org/10.7937/K9/TCIA.2015.NWTESAY1>"

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code for the challenge is publicly released (furthermore, exemplary "ready to go" algorithms are provided as well). See <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood> .

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

All participating teams appear on the leaderboard (if they choose). However (to prevent misconduct) only teams that open source their code will be eligible to win the challenge and receive any prizes.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Currently, there is no explicit sponsoring of the challenge (the workforce is currently funded by DKFZ and Helmholtz Imaging).

Access to test cases will only be given to individual members of the organizers involved in the evaluation process.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education

- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Diagnosis, Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Out-of-Distribution Detection (Classification)

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The goal of this approach is to detect (incidental) findings and improve inattentive blindness. Thus, anyone having an MRI/CT scan, for which a model was trained, would be in a target cohort.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

For our challenge cohort the subjects are:

Brain: healthy young adult participants (see more: <https://www.humanconnectome.org/study/hcp-youngadult/document/1200-subjects-data-release>)

Abdominal: Male and female outpatients, aged 50 years or older, scheduled for screening colonoscopy, who have not had a colonoscopy in the past 5 years (see more: <https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/CT+COLONOGRAPHY>).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Brain: MRT (T2)

Abdominal: CT

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The advantage and goal of the challenge is to evaluate models that are not specific to a distinct body part or scan. So if enough data or an already trained model is available all body regions appearing in medical imaging scans (CT/MRI) could be used as a target for the algorithms.

However, given the available data, we only provide two different data origins, head MRI and abdominal CT. For those datasets, the same algorithm should be trained and evaluated.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target in our case is anything that deviates from the given training distribution, i.e. Anomalies / Out-of-(training) distribution images. In particular, the idea is to differentiate between natural anatomic deviations and pathological conditions, thus detecting anomalies/ abnormal parts. However, to ensure a controlled setting and allow for a fair and highly controlled evaluation of the algorithms, we use samples for testing that are derived from the same distribution as was used for training purposes. Anomalies will be artificially introduced.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Average Precision

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Brain:

"All HCP subjects are scanned on a customized Siemens 3T "Connectome Skyra" housed at Washington University in St. Louis, using a standard 32-channel Siemens receive head coil and a "body" transmission coil designed by Siemens specifically for the smaller space available using the special gradients of the WU-Minn and MGH-UCLA Connectome scanners. The scanner has a customized SC72 gradient insert and a customized body transmitter coil with 56 cm bore size (diffusion: $G_{max} = 100$ mT/m, max slew rate = 91 mT/m/ms; readout/imaging: $G_{max} = 42$ mT/m, max slew rate = 200 mT/m/ms). The HCP Skyra has the standard set of Siemens shim coils (up to 2nd order). Relative to a standard commercial Skyra, the customized hardware includes a gradient coil and gradient power amplifiers that together increase the maximum gradient strength from 40 mT/m to 100 mT/m on the WUMinn 3T. This specifically benefits diffusion imaging, and on theoretical grounds (gurbil et al. 2013) it should provide significant gains over the standard 40 mT/m though not as much as the 300 mT/m customized gradients used by the MGH/UCLA HCP consortium. Head motion and physiological monitoring. To address head motion, in most scan sessions we acquire dynamic head position information using an optical motion tracking camera system (Moire Phase Tracker, Kineticon). This system monitors head position precisely and in real-time using an infrared camera mounted in the scanner bore. Images of Moire interference fringes on a target affixed by clay to the bridge of the subjects nose are streamed in real-time to a computer that displays the current position of the sensor and stores the positional information in a data file linked to the associated MRI scan. The stored file of head position and head movement can be used for post-hoc analyses. We also use it as a feedback trigger in dMRI scans to interrupt the movie being viewed whenever suprathreshold displacement and/or rapid head movement occur. Positional information can also be routed to the MRI scanner computer and can in principle be used prospectively to update the MRI slice prescription in real-time (Zaitsev et al., 2006). However, prospective motion correction is not part of our 3T HCP acquisition protocol because the technology became available only late in the HCP method development phase and was not sufficiently tested and developed before the data collection protocol was finalized (Van Essen et al., 2013)."

see

https://www.humanconnectome.org/storage/app/media/documentation/s1200/HCP_S1200_Release_Reference_

Manual.pdf for more information

Abdominal:

"A total of 15 clinical sites participated in this HIPAA-compliant study, and approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board at each site prior to activation. Subjects were recruited from among all asymptomatic patients 50 years or older, prescheduled for routine colonoscopy at the participating sites between February 2005 and December 2006. Exclusion criteria were melena and/or hematochezia on more than one occasion in the previous six months, lower abdominal pain, inflammatory bowel disease and/or familial polyposis syndrome, serious medical conditions associated with excessive colonoscopy risk, colonoscopy within the previous five years, anemia (hemoglobin less than 10 gm/dl), or positive fecal occult blood test (FOBT). Each enrolled study participant provided written informed consent.[...]

Supine and prone data acquisitions were obtained. All examinations were performed using at least a 16 slice CT scanner. Images were acquired using 0.5-1.0 mm collimation, pitch of 0.98-1.5, matrix 512 × 512, field-of-view to fit, 50 effective mAs, 120 kVp, and standard reconstruction algorithm. Images for prone and supine acquisitions were reconstructed to slice thicknesses of 1-1.25 mm with a 0.8 mm reconstruction interval.(7)"

For more information see: <https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/CT+COLONOGRAPHY>

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See a)

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

See a)

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

See a)

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Brain:

Training and test cases both represent MRI images of human brains.

Abdominal:

Training and test cases both represent CT images of human abdominal tracts.

The training cases have no annotations. The test cases either come from the same training distribution or another distribution e.g. by altering the images, i.e. introducing anomalies. For the test images, information on the original distribution labels and anomaly segmentations are maintained.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Brain: Training: 800, Testing 688, (4 for Feedback)

Abdominal: Training 550, Testing: 599, (4 for Feedback)

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Since a part of our test-cases is artificially created, we can generate a high number of different test-cases (however the minimal amount of test cases is determined by the normal part of the test-case, and to prevent any fine-tuning of the scores to this ratio, we choose not to disclose the exact number of cases. However, if it would be useful, we can share this information with the reviewers, if they agree not to take part in the challenge). To get a fair comparison with high significance, we aim for a 50%-50% split between training and test data. Considering the time needed for evaluation, this results in 800 training and 688 test cases for the brain dataset and 550 training and 599 test cases for the abdominal dataset (each testset having a fixed normal/abnormal split).

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Since we use publicly available data and to prevent misconduct we do not fully disclose our testing data distribution (since the goal is to detect potentially unknown anomalies). However, we are willing to share this information with the reviewers, if it would be helpful (and if the reviewers agree not to take part in the challenge).

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All of our test data is unseen and unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For the sample-level task, a few selected naturally occurring conditions were chosen and excluded from the test set. The results were checked by at least two humans (checked individually, then a fixed common labeling protocol was agreed on, and then all cases were checked again). Furthermore, the results were checked semi-automatically multiple times.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Since this would reveal too much information and to prevent cheating we do not fully disclose this information and are willing you share it with the reviewers if it would be helpful (and if the reviewers agree not to take part in the challenge).

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Since this would reveal too much information and to prevent cheating we do not fully disclose this information and are willing you share it with the reviewers if it would be helpful. However, the results were checked by at least two humans (checked individually, then a fixed common labeling protocol was agreed on, and then all cases were checked again). Furthermore, the results were checked semi-automatically multiple times.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Checked individually, then a fixed common labeling protocol was agreed on, and then all cases were checked again

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For all sets, we perform the same preprocessing. We resample, crop and intensity-shift the images. This makes the preprocessed training samples and the preprocessed (unmodified) testing samples still originate from the same distribution. However, since we use publicly available data and to prevent cheating we do not fully disclose our preprocessing and are willing you share it with the reviewers if it would be helpful (and if the reviewers agree not to take part in the challenge).

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We generate the anomalies artificially with full control over their shape and appearance. Thus, there should be no errors in the annotation. We have already tested the anomaly generation code for some time and believe that it is free of errors. However, since we only use the labels for testing, potential remaining bugs do not affect training and scores could be simply recomputed after fixing cases and labels. This would lead to an update of the leaderboard.

It is possible that "true" anomalies appear in the training set. This could potentially include cases such as polyps, that were not detected by a radiologist, or a patient with an abnormal kidney, that was overseen since it was not the indication for the examination. Such cases would be expected to be learned as "normal" since they are part of the training distribution. There is a highly unlikely case, in which an artificially introduced anomaly by coincidence is very similar to some of these "true" abnormalities missed during the inspection of the training set. Even if this unlikely case occurs, it will not influence the overall results too much given the size of the testset (and it is the same for all participants).

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

see above

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Average Precision (AP), which "summarizes a precision-recall curve as the weighted mean of precisions achieved at each threshold, with the increase in recall from the previous threshold used as the weight" (https://scikitlearn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.metrics.average_precision_score.html) . For more information see [9] or https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.metrics.average_precision_score.html.

Our evaluation code can be found here: <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood>

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

We chose AP since it is more robust to AUROC with regard to class imbalance (despite us being able to control it and keep it at 1/2 to 2/3) and has been suggested by many recent papers [2,3,4,6,9]. However, since this is the among most used and often recommended metrics we chose AP, but after the challenge might investigate different metrics, such as object-level detection metrics (choosing an abnormality threshold based on a hold-out validation set similar to [23]) and present it in the paper as well as on the leaderboard (e.g. AUROC, FPR@95).

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We chose AP since it is more robust to AUROC with regard to class imbalance (despite us being able to control it and keep it at 1/2 to 2/3) and has been suggested by many recent papers [2,3,4,6,9]. However, since this is the among most used and often recommended metrics we chose AP, but after the challenge might investigate different metrics and present them in the paper as well as on the leaderboard (e.g. AUROC, FPR@95).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Since we use docker-based testing we assume that almost all participants will process all cases. However, should one case be not considered, we will assign it the lowest given anomaly score (= 0).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For each sample, the users should report an anomaly score, indicating the certainty of detecting the anomaly in the given image. We expect the scores to be in the interval [0-1], where 0 is the lowest score indicating no abnormality and 1 is the highest score indicating the most abnormal input (Scores above and below the interval will be clamped to [0-1]). We will use the reported scores together with the ground truth labels to calculate the AP over the whole dataset. The ranking for one dataset will then be given by the AP over the whole dataset. We combine the two datasets by choosing a consolidation ranking schema.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,

- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Stability will be investigated via bootstrapping and hypothesis testing (using challengeR, code available at github: <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood>, results from last year available at: <http://medicalood.dkfz.de/docs/>). We will further investigate the confidence intervals (CI) of the methods.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Bootstrapping was identified as an appropriate approach to investigate ranking variability in [24, Maier-Hein et al 2018]

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Since we can control and differentiate different kinds, scales, and intensities of anomalies, even for the same test cases, similar to last year, we further plan to investigate which algorithm is able to detect which kind of anomaly reliably or with less certainty.

We will further show the FPR at certain thresholds and the resulting TP, FPs, and FNs,

TASK 2: Object-Level

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In addition to identifying entire images with anomalies, pinpointing the exact location of abnormalities is crucial for guiding physician diagnosis and understanding. This pixel/object-level task challenges participants to develop algorithms that accurately localize and segment clinically relevant anomalies within medical images (e.g., brain MRI, abdominal CT).

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

N/A

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

David Zimmerer, Gregor Köhler, Peter Full, Klaus Maier-Hein

Div. Medical Image Computing (MIC), German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)

Annika Reinke, Lena Maier-Hein

Div Computer Assisted Medical Interventions (CAMI), German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

David Zimmerer (MIC, DKFZ) d.zimmerer@dkfz.de

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://synapse.org/mood>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

No prizes have yet been determined. Currently, the winner will win the right to brag about the results.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

By default (i.e. if they don't decline) the top 3 (winning) teams will be announced publicly. The remaining teams may decide if they choose to appear on the public Leaderboard.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participating teams with a valid submission. Teams that reveal their identity, can nominate members of their team as co-authors for the challenge paper (as many members as the team wants). However, we reserve the right to exclude teams and team members if they do not adhere to the challenge rules and guidelines.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/mood>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Teams are allowed three submissions per challenge task, however, only the latest submission will be considered. For each challenge submission, the teams will receive the results on a very simple "toy" test-case, which will not be included in the final testset. We also already made the "toy" case and testing script publicly available so that the participants can check beforehand if their submission won't cause any errors and to compare the reported results with their own to check for any additional occurring errors. Additionally, a dedicated toy-case evaluation queue will be available where participants can submit their solutions to our cluster and only run the toy cases and receive toy-case results. This toy-case evaluation queue will not count as a challenge submission, will have no submission limit, and only serve as a "will run successfully" check.

We may offer rankings only (no scores) on a toy subset of the test set to give participants some directional feedback.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Release of training cases: 15 March 2025

Registration Until: 15 August 2025

Submission of Dockers: 16 August 2025

Invitation of the participants to present their results: 1 September 2025

Release date of the results: MICCAI 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The provided challenge data is anonymized.

According to [Euro2016], the anonymized data can be used for the challenge.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

For the Brain Data the following Licence applies: "I will not attempt to establish the identity of or attempt to contact any of the included human subjects. I understand that under no circumstances will the code that would link these data to Protected Health Information be given to me, nor will any additional information about individual human subjects be released to me under these Open Access Data Use Terms. I will comply with all relevant rules and regulations imposed by my institution. This may mean that I need my research to be approved or declared exempt by a committee that oversees research on human subjects, e.g. my IRB or Ethics Committee. The released HCP data are not considered de-identified, insofar as certain combinations of HCP Restricted Data (available through a separate process) might allow identification of individuals. Different committees operate under different national, state and local laws and may interpret regulations differently, so it is important to ask about this. If needed and upon request, the HCP will provide a certificate stating that you have accepted the HCP Open Access Data Use Terms. I may redistribute original WU-Minn HCP Open Access data and any derived data as long as the data are redistributed under these same Data Use Terms. I will acknowledge the use of WU-Minn HCP data and data derived from WU-Minn HCP data when publicly presenting any results or algorithms that benefitted from their use. Papers, book chapters, books, posters, oral presentations, and all other printed and digital presentations of results derived from HCP data should contain the following wording in the acknowledgments section: "Data were provided [in part] by the Human Connectome Project, WU-Minn Consortium (Principal Investigators: David Van Essen and Kamil Ugurbil; 1U54MH091657) funded by the 16 NIH Institutes and Centers that support the NIH Blueprint for Neuroscience Research; and by the McDonnell Center for Systems Neuroscience at Washington University." Authors of publications or presentations using WU-Minn HCP data should cite relevant publications describing the methods used by the HCP to acquire and process the data. The specific publications that are appropriate to cite in any given study will depend on what HCP data were used and for what purposes. An annotated and appropriately up-to-date list of publications that may warrant consideration is available at <http://www.humanconnectome.org/about/acknowledgehcp.html> The WU-Minn HCP Consortium as a whole should not be included as an author of publications or presentations if this authorship would be based solely on the use of WU-Minn HCP data. Failure to abide by these guidelines will result in termination of my privileges to access WU-Minn HCP data." For the Abdominal data the following Licence applies: "Citations & Data Usage Policy This collection is freely available to browse, download, and use for commercial, scientific and educational purposes as outlined in the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License. See TCIA's Data Usage Policies and Restrictions for additional details. Questions may be directed to help@cancerimagingarchive.net. Please be sure to include the following citations in your work if you use this data

set: Data CitationSmith K, Clark K, Bennett W, Nolan T, Kirby J, Wolfsberger M, Moulton J, Vendt B, Freymann J. (2015). Data From CT_COLONOGRAPHY. The Cancer Imaging Archive. <http://doi.org/10.7937/K9/TCIA.2015.NWTESAY1>"

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code for the challenge is publicly released (furthermore, exemplary "ready to go" algorithms are provided as well). See <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood> .

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

All participating teams appear on the leaderboard (if they choose). However (to prevent misconduct) only teams that open source their code will be eligible to win the challenge and receive any prizes.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Currently, there is no explicit sponsoring of the challenge (the workforce is currently funded by DKFZ and Helmholtz Imaging).

Access to test cases will only be given to individual members of the organizers involved in the evaluation process.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research,Diagnosis,Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Out-of-Distribution Detection (Localization)

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The goal of this approach is to detect (incidental) findings and improve inattentive blindness. Thus, anyone having an MRI/CT scan, for which a model was trained, would be in a target cohort.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

For our challenge cohort the subjects are:

Brain: healthy young adult participants (see more: <https://www.humanconnectome.org/study/hcp-youngadult/document/1200-subjects-data-release>)

Abdominal: Male and female outpatients, aged 50 years or older, scheduled for screening colonoscopy, who have not had a colonoscopy in the past 5 years (see more:

<https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/CT+COLONOGRAPHY>).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Brain: MRT (T2)

Abdominal: CT

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The advantage and goal of the challenge is to evaluate models that are not specific to a distinct body part or scan. So if enough data or an already trained model is available all body regions appearing in medical imaging scans (CT/MRI) could be used as a target for the algorithms.

However, given the available data, we only provide two different data origins, head MRI and abdominal CT. For those datasets, the same algorithm should be trained and evaluated.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target in our case is anything that deviates from the given training distribution, i.e. Anomalies / Out-of-(training) distribution images. In particular, the idea is to differentiate between natural anatomic deviations and pathological conditions, thus detecting anomalies/ abnormal parts. However, to ensure a controlled setting and allow for a fair and highly controlled evaluation of the algorithms, we use samples for testing that are derived from the same distribution as was used for training purposes. Anomalies will be artificially introduced.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Detected Objects

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Brain:

"All HCP subjects are scanned on a customized Siemens 3T "Connectome Skyra" housed at Washington University in St. Louis, using a standard 32-channel Siemens receive head coil and a "body" transmission coil designed by Siemens specifically for the smaller space available using the special gradients of the WU-Minn and MGH-UCLA Connectome scanners. The scanner has a customized SC72 gradient insert and a customized body transmitter coil with 56 cm bore size (diffusion: $G_{max} = 100$ mT/m, max slew rate = 91 mT/m/ms; readout/imaging: $G_{max} = 42$ mT/m, max slew rate = 200 mT/m/ms). The HCP Skyra has the standard set of Siemens shim coils (up to 2nd order). Relative to a standard commercial Skyra, the customized hardware includes a gradient coil and gradient power amplifiers that together increase the maximum gradient strength from 40 mT/m to 100 mT/m on the WUMinn 3T. This specifically benefits diffusion imaging, and on theoretical grounds (gurbil et al. 2013) it should provide significant gains over the standard 40 mT/m though not as much as the 300 mT/m customized gradients used by the MGH/UCLA HCP consortium. Head motion and physiological monitoring. To address head motion, in most scan sessions we acquire dynamic head position information using an optical motion tracking camera system (Moire Phase Tracker, Kineticon). This system monitors head position precisely and in real-time using an infrared camera mounted in the scanner bore. Images of Moire interference fringes on a target affixed by clay to the bridge of the subjects nose are streamed in real-time to a computer that displays the current position of the sensor and stores the positional information in a data file linked to the associated MRI scan. The stored file of head position and head movement can be used for post-hoc analyses. We also use it as a feedback trigger in dMRI scans to interrupt the movie being viewed whenever suprathreshold displacement and/or rapid head movement occur. Positional information can also be routed to the MRI scanner computer and can in principle be used prospectively to update the MRI slice prescription in real-time (Zaitsev et al., 2006). However, prospective motion correction is not part of our 3T HCP acquisition protocol because the technology became available only late in the HCP method development phase and was not sufficiently tested and developed before the data collection protocol was finalized (Van Essen et al., 2013)."

see

https://www.humanconnectome.org/storage/app/media/documentation/s1200/HCP_S1200_Release_Reference_Manual.pdf for more information

Abdominal:

"A total of 15 clinical sites participated in this HIPAA-compliant study, and approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board at each site prior to activation. Subjects were recruited from among all asymptomatic patients 50 years or older, prescheduled for routine colonoscopy at the participating sites between February 2005 and December 2006. Exclusion criteria were melena and/or hematochezia on more than one occasion in the previous six months, lower abdominal pain, inflammatory bowel disease and/or familial polyposis syndrome, serious medical conditions associated with excessive colonoscopy risk, colonoscopy within the previous five years, anemia (hemoglobin less than 10 gm/dl), or positive fecal occult blood test (FOBT). Each enrolled study participant provided written informed consent.[...]

Supine and prone data acquisitions were obtained. All examinations were performed using at least a 16 slice CT scanner. Images were acquired using 0.5-1.0 mm collimation, pitch of 0.98-1.5, matrix 512 × 512, field-of-view to fit, 50 effective mAs, 120 kVp, and standard reconstruction algorithm. Images for prone and supine acquisitions

were reconstructed to slice thicknesses of 1-1.25 mm with a 0.8 mm reconstruction interval.(7)"

For more information see: <https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/CT+COLONOGRAPHY>

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See a)

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

See a)

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

See a)

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Brain:

Training and test cases both represent MRI images of human brains.

Abdominal:

Training and test cases both represent CT images of human abdominal tracts.

The training cases have no annotations. The test cases either come from the same training distribution or another distribution e.g. by altering the images, i.e. introducing anomalies. For the test images, information on the original distribution labels and anomaly segmentations are maintained.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Brain: Training: 800, Testing 542, (4 for Feedback)

Abdominal: Training 550, Testing: 358, (4 for Feedback)

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Since a part of our test-cases is artificially created, we can generate a high number of different test-cases (however the minimal amount of test cases is determined by the normal part of the test-case, and to prevent any fine-tuning of the scores to this ratio, we choose not to disclose the exact number of cases. However, if it would be useful, we can share this information with the reviewers, if they agree not to take part in the challenge). To get

a fair comparison with high significance, we aim for a 50%-50% split between training and test data. Considering the time needed for evaluation, this results in 800 training and 688 test cases for the brain dataset and 550 training and 599 test cases for the abdominal dataset (each testset having a fixed normal/abnormal split).

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Since we use publicly available data and to prevent misconduct we do not fully disclose our testing data distribution (since the goal is to detect potentially unknown anomalies). However, we are willing to share this information with the reviewers, if it would be helpful (and if the reviewers agree not to take part in the challenge).

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All of our test data is unseen and unpublished.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For the sample-level task, a few selected naturally occurring conditions were chosen and excluded from the test set. The results were checked by at least two humans (checked individually, then a fixed common labeling protocol was agreed on, and then all cases were checked again). Furthermore, the results were checked semi-automatically multiple times.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Since this would reveal too much information and to prevent cheating we do not fully disclose this information and are willing you share it with the reviewers if it would be helpful (and if the reviewers agree not to take part in the challenge).

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Since this would reveal too much information and to prevent cheating we do not fully disclose this information and are willing you share it with the reviewers if it would be helpful. However, the results were checked by at least two humans (checked individually, then a fixed common labeling protocol was agreed on, and then all cases were checked again). Furthermore, the results were checked semi-automatically multiple times.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Checked individually, then a fixed common labeling protocol was agreed on, and then all cases were checked again

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For all sets, we perform the same preprocessing. We resample, crop and intensity-shift the images. This makes the preprocessed training samples and the preprocessed (unmodified) testing samples still originate from the same distribution. However, since we use publicly available data and to prevent cheating we do not fully disclose our preprocessing and are willing you share it with the reviewers if it would be helpful (and if the reviewers agree not to take part in the challenge).

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We generate the anomalies artificially with full control over their shape and appearance. Thus, there should be no errors in the annotation. We have already tested the anomaly generation code for some time and believe that it is free of errors. However, since we only use the labels for testing, potential remaining bugs do not affect training and scores could be simply recomputed after fixing cases and labels. This would lead to an update of the leaderboard.

It is possible that "true" anomalies appear in the training set. This could potentially include cases such as polyps, that were not detected by a radiologist, or a patient with an abnormal kidney, that was overseen since it was not the indication for the examination. Such cases would be expected to be learned as "normal" since they are part of the training distribution. There is a highly unlikely case, in which an artificially introduced anomaly by coincidence is very similar to some of these "true" abnormalities missed during the inspection of the training set. Even if this unlikely case occurs, it will not influence the overall results too much given the size of the testset (and it is the same for all participants).

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

see above

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

As it was successful for last year's edition and corresponded more closely to a human-aligned metric, in contrast to AP, we here opt for a more object-centric metric.

Here a GT object is either given by a rendered object or a (connected) segmented (natural) anomaly.

A prediction object is obtained in the following way: The participants can decide if they want to submit a binary prediction (0 or 1) or a continuous score (0-1). In the case of a continuous score, we use a toy-dataset (similar to the toy-dataset presented to the participants) to determine the best binarization threshold with respect to the

presented metric on this toy-dataset. We then use the binarization threshold to binarize the continuous score. On the binarized score, we apply connected component analysis to find individual objects and discard all objects that are smaller than half the size of the smallest anomaly in our test set and all objects with are more than two times bigger than the biggest object in our test set (to sort out low-frequency noise). This procedure then outputs the prediction objects.

We then match the GT objects and the prediction objects in the following way to obtain TP, FP, FN:

If the center of mass of the prediction object falls in the convex hull of the GT object and the size difference is only at max a factor of two ($= 0.5 * \text{GT-object size} < \text{prediction-object size} < 2 * \text{GT-object size}$), then we consider the GT object to be detected, resulting in a TP. If a GT object was not matched/detected by any prediction object we consider this an FN. If a prediction object could not be matched to a GT object, we consider this an FP. We iterate over all images and objects in the dataset and obtain all TP, FP, FN for the whole dataset. The final score is then given by the F1 score (using the determined TPs, FPs, FNs).

Our evaluation code will be available here: <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood>

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

We chose this metric in contrast to AP since this better matched the objective of localizing and detecting an abnormal image part. AP, similar to dice, tends to put disproportional importance on 'big' objects, which, even despite batching, can mask some undetected objects. Here an object-detection-based metric can be more fitting. We opted for this center of mass and size-based matching and not an IoU-based score since we found this better aligns with the detection of an object which could then be presented to a physician for further review than an arbitrary IoU threshold. An expert radiologist confirmed this to be a reasonable approach.

This was further compared to other metrics and a human rater in [27].

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Since scans in the test set can be normal and contain no anomalies and scans might contain multiple anomalies, a per-case score is not optimal (as it would have a high per-scan variance and give very extreme values). Thus we first calculate a whole-dataset score and then combine the different datasets with consolidation ranking (giving both datasets the same importance). This code has been previously tested on multiple in-house projects (e.g. [26]) where the predictions have been reviewed by an expert radiologist and the code was made public for last year's edition.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Since we use docker-based testing we assume that almost all participants will process all cases. However, should one case be not considered, we will assign it 0 TPs, FPs, and FNs (similar to an 'all 0' prediction).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For each voxel, the users should report an anomaly score, indicating the certainty of detecting the anomaly for the given voxels. We expect the scores to be in the interval [0-1], where 0 is the lowest score indicating no abnormality and 1 is the highest score indicating the most abnormal input (Scores above and below the interval will be clamped to [0-1]) or binary [0,1]. We will use the reported scores together with the ground truth labels to

calculate the TPs, FPs, FNs over the whole dataset. The ranking for one dataset will then be given by the F1 over the whole dataset (given the TPs, FPs, FNs). We combine the two datasets by choosing a consolidation ranking schema.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Stability will be investigated via bootstrapping and hypothesis testing (using challengeR, code available at github: <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood>, results from last year available at: <http://medicalood.dkfz.de/docs/>). We will further investigate the confidence intervals (CI) of the methods.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Bootstrapping was identified as an appropriate approach to investigate ranking variability in [24, Maier-Hein et al 2018]

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Since we can control and differentiate different kinds, scales, and intensities of anomalies, even for the same test cases, similar to last year, we further plan to investigate which algorithm is able to detect which kind of anomaly reliably or with less certainty.

We will further show the FPR and the resulting TP, FPs, and FNs,

TASK 3: Real-World Anomaly Detection

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The Real-World "Open-World" Anomaly Detection task introduces a clinically motivated challenge inspired by the interesting and rare neuro-radiological cases discussed in journals. This task focuses on detecting and localizing anomalies across a diverse set of real-world neuroradiology cases, reflecting the variability and complexity encountered in clinical practice. The dataset includes a wide spectrum of neurological conditions, such as brain tumors, vascular diseases, infections, degenerative diseases, congenital anomalies, trauma, and other miscellaneous pathologies. Each case is meticulously labeled by an expert radiologist, ensuring high-quality annotations that reflect clinical relevance.

Participants are tasked with localizing anomalies within these cases, using any training data or models of their choice. Unlike traditional benchmarks, the emphasis is on solving the medical task rather than adhering to fixed datasets or constraints. This open-ended approach encourages innovative solutions tailored to real-world challenges, where conditions are rare, varied, and often subtle. By evaluating performance on these richly diverse cases, this task aims to bridge the gap between academic research and clinical applicability, fostering the development of robust anomaly detection models that align with the needs of modern neuroradiology.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

N/A

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Cosmin Bercea, Julia Schnabel

Computational Imaging and AI in Medicine, TUM School of Computation, Information, and Technology

Benedikt Wiestler

AI for Image-Guided Diagnosis and Therapy School of Medicine & Health

David Zimmerer, Gregor Köhler, Peter Full, Klaus Maier-Hein

Div. Medical Image Computing (MIC), German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)

Annika Reinke, Lena Maier-Hein

Div Computer Assisted Medical Interventions (CAMI), German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Cosmin Bercea (TUM) cosmin.bercea@tum.de

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://synapse.org/mood>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No policy defined

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

No prizes have yet been determined. Currently, the winner will win the right to brag about the results.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

By default (i.e. if they don't decline) the top 3 (winning) teams will be announced publicly. The remaining teams may decide if they choose to appear on the public Leaderboard.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participating teams with a valid submission. Teams that reveal their identity, can nominate members of their team as co-authors for the challenge paper (as many members as the team wants). However, we reserve the right to exclude teams and team members if they do not adhere to the challenge rules and guidelines.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/mood>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Teams are allowed three submissions per challenge task, however, only the latest submission will be considered. For each challenge submission, the teams will receive the results on a very simple "toy" test-case, which will not be included in the final testset. We also already made the "toy" case and testing script publicly available so that the participants can check beforehand if their submission won't cause any errors and to compare the reported results with their own to check for any additional occurring errors. Additionally, a dedicated toy-case evaluation queue will be available where participants can submit their solutions to our cluster and only run the toy cases and receive toy-case results. This toy-case evaluation queue will not count as a challenge submission, will have no submission limit, and only serve as a "will run successfully" check.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

No training cases will be released.

Registration Until: 15 August 2025

Submission of Dockers: 16 August 2025

Invitation of the participants to present their results: 1 September 2025

Release date of the results: MICCAI 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The provided challenge data is anonymized.

According to [Euro2016], the anonymized data can be used for the challenge.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

We do not release any data in/ for this task

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code for the challenge will be publicly released (furthermore, exemplary "ready to go" algorithms are provided as well). See <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood> .

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

All participating teams appear on the leaderboard (if they choose). However (to prevent misconduct) only teams that open source their code will be eligible to win the challenge and receive any prizes.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Currently, there is no explicit sponsoring of the challenge (the workforce is currently funded by TUM, DKFZ and Helmholtz Imaging).

Access to test cases will only be given to individual members of the organizers involved in the evaluation process.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Out-of-Distribution Detection (Localization)

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The goal of this approach is to detect (incidental) findings and improve inattentive blindness. Thus, anyone having an MRI/CT scan, for which a model was trained, would be in a target cohort.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

In the case reports, images from a wide range of patients across the entire age span (from small children to elderly) are included.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI, CT, PET CT, SPECT

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Head-region

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Algorithms should detect any pathology, in particular rare diseases.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Detected Objects

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The data source for this "in the wild" challenge features a diverse array of imaging modalities and devices. The dataset comprises images and accompanying reports submitted by a large, international community of physicians. These cases were curated and presented as notable "Case-of-the-Week" discussions, highlighting their clinical significance.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See a)

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

See a)

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

See a)

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context

information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Brain:

A test cases both represent medical images of human heads, with detected anomalies (bounding boxes).

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

We don't publish dedicated training images, as all images can be used, as well as the images provided for task 1&2.

Testing 400, Validation 5.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Since we don't provide any training data, all data we use is purely for testing.

To prohibit any overfitting to the test data, we only allow 5 samples for validation.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Since we use publicly available data and to prevent misconduct we do not fully disclose our testing data distribution (since the goal is to detect potentially unknown anomalies). However, we are willing to share this information with the reviewers, if it would be helpful (and if the reviewers agree not to take part in the challenge).

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The annotations of the test data are unseen and unpublished. Furthermore, we do not disclose which cases we use for testing.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The reference annotations (bounding boxes), were generated by at least one experienced neuroradiologist (board-certified).

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The radiologists received the scan together with the report/ described pathologies and other markings available with the instruction to annotate the bounding box around the described pathology.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

At least one board-certified neuroradiologist (>10 years of experience); all radiologists are medically trained with different levels of experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We used consensus merging by computing weighted averaging of the bounding box coordinates according to the reviewer's experience level.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For all sets, we perform the same preprocessing. We resample, crop and intensity-shift the images. This makes the preprocessed training samples and the preprocessed (unmodified) testing samples still originate from the same distribution. However, since we use publicly available data and to prevent cheating we do not fully disclose our preprocessing and are willing you share it with the reviewers if it would be helpful (and if the reviewers agree not to take part in the challenge).

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

As the cases were reviewed multiple times and were based on published and reviewed clinical documentation, we think the chances of an error are marginal. We will add information about the inter-annotator variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Perhaps undetected conditions are present in the images and were missed during the inspection of the test set. Even if this unlikely case occurs, it will not influence the overall results too much given the size of the testset (and it is the same for all participants).

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

As it was successful for last year's edition and corresponded more closely to a human-aligned metric, in contrast to AP, we here opt for a more object-centric metric.

Here a GT object is either given by a rendered object or a (connected) segmented (natural) anomaly.

A prediction object is obtained in the following way: The participants can decide if they want to submit a binary prediction (0 or 1) or a continuous score (0-1). In the case of a continuous score, we use a toy-dataset (similar to the toy-dataset presented to the participants) to determine the best binarization threshold with respect to the presented metric on this toy-dataset. We then use the binarization threshold to binarize the continuous score. On the binarized score, we apply connected component analysis to find individual objects and discard all objects that

are smaller than half the size of the smallest anomaly in our test set and all objects with are more than two times bigger than the biggest object in our test set (to sort out low-frequency noise). This procedure then outputs the prediction objects.

We then match the GT objects and the prediction objects in the following way to obtain TP, FP, FN:

If the center of mass of the prediction object falls in the convex hull of the GT object and the size difference is only at max a factor of two ($= 0.5 * \text{GT-object size} < \text{prediction-object size} < 2 * \text{GT-object size}$), then we consider the GT object to be detected, resulting in a TP. If a GT object was not matched/detected by any prediction object we consider this an FN. If a prediction object could not be matched to a GT object, we consider this an FP. We iterate over all images and objects in the dataset and obtain all TP, FP, FN for the whole dataset. The final score is then given by the F1 score (using the determined TPs, FPs, FNs).

Our evaluation code will be available here: <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood>

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

We chose this metric in contrast to AP since this better matched the objective of localizing and detecting an abnormal image part. AP, similar to dice, tends to put disproportional importance on 'big' objects, which, even despite batching, can mask some undetected objects. Here an object-detection-based metric can be more fitting. We opted for this center of mass and size-based matching and not an IoU-based score since we found this better aligns with the detection of an object which could then be presented to a physician for further review than an arbitrary IoU threshold. An expert radiologist confirmed this to be a reasonable approach.

This was further compared to other metrics and a human rater in [27].

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Since scans in the test set can be normal and contain no anomalies and scans might contain multiple anomalies, a per-case score is not optimal (as it would have a high per-scan variance and give very extreme values). Thus we first calculate a whole-dataset score and then combine the different datasets with consolidation ranking (giving both datasets the same importance). This code has been previously tested on multiple in-house projects (e.g. [26]) where the predictions have been reviewed by an expert radiologist and the code was made public for last year's edition.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Since we use docker-based testing we assume that almost all participants will process all cases. However, should one case be not considered, we will assign it 0 TPs, FPs, and FNs (similar to an 'all 0' prediction).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For each voxel, the users should report an anomaly score, indicating the certainty of detecting the anomaly for the given voxels. We expect the scores to be in the interval [0-1], where 0 is the lowest score indicating no abnormality and 1 is the highest score indicating the most abnormal input (Scores above and below the interval will be clamped to [0-1]) or binary [0,1]. We will use the reported scores together with the ground truth labels to calculate the TPs, FPs, FNs over the whole dataset. The ranking for one dataset will then be given by the F1 over the whole dataset (given the TPs, FPs, FNs). We combine the two datasets by choosing a consolidation ranking

schema.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Stability will be investigated via bootstrapping and hypothesis testing (using challengeR, code available at github: <https://github.com/MIC-DKFZ/mood>, results from last year available at: <http://medicalood.dkfz.de/docs/>). We will further investigate the confidence intervals (CI) of the methods.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Bootstrapping was identified as an appropriate approach to investigate ranking variability in [24, Maier-Hein et al 2018]

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We can stratify the results based on classes of different anomalies (types, family of pathology, size, etc..) to assess what types of anomalies can detect (similar to task 1 & 2).

We will further show the FPR and the resulting TP, FPs, and FNs,

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

[1] Drew, Trafton, Melissa L. H. Vo, and Jeremy M. Wolfe. "The Invisible Gorilla Strikes Again: Sustained Inattention Blindness in Expert Observers." *Psychological Science* 24, no. 9 (September 2013): 1848-53. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797613479386>.

[2] Bergmann, Paul, Michael Fauser, David Sattlegger, and Carsten Steger. "MVTec AD -- A Comprehensive Real-World Dataset for Unsupervised Anomaly Detection," 9592-9600, 2019. http://openaccess.thecvf.com/content_CVPR_2019/html/Bergmann_MVTec_AD_-_A_Comprehensive_Real-World_Dataset_for_Unsupervised_Anomaly_CVPR_2019_paper.html.

[3] Hendrycks, Dan, Steven Basart, Mantas Mazeika, Mohammadreza Mostajabi, Jacob Steinhardt, and Dawn

- Song. "A Benchmark for Anomaly Segmentation." ArXiv:1911.11132 [Cs], November 25, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1911.11132>.
- [4] Chen, Xiaoran, Nick Pawlowski, Martin Rajchl, Ben Glocker, and Ender Konukoglu. "Deep Generative Models in the Real-World: An Open Challenge from Medical Imaging." CoRR abs/1806.05452 (2018).
- [5] Baur, Christoph, Benedikt Wiestler, Shadi Albarqouni, and Nassir Navab. "Deep Autoencoding Models for Unsupervised Anomaly Segmentation in Brain MR Images." ArXiv:1804.04488 [Cs], April 12, 2018. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1804.04488>.
- [6] Zimmerer, David, Fabian Isensee, Jens Petersen, Simon Kohl, and Klaus Maier-Hein. "Unsupervised Anomaly Localization Using Variational Auto-Encoders." In International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention, 289-297. Springer, 2019.
- [7] Schlegl, Thomas, Philipp Seeböck, Sebastian M Waldstein, Ursula Schmidt-Erfurth, and Georg Langs. "Unsupervised Anomaly Detection with Generative Adversarial Networks to Guide Marker Discovery," n.d. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1703.05921.pdf>.
- [8] Abati, Davide, Angelo Porrello, Simone Calderara, and Rita Cucchiara. "Latent Space Autoregression for Novelty Detection." ArXiv:1807.01653 [Cs], July 4, 2018. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1807.01653>.
- [9] Ahmed, Faruk, and Aaron Courville. "Detecting Semantic Anomalies." ArXiv:1908.04388 [Cs], August 13, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1908.04388>.
- [10] Akcay, Samet, Amir Atapour-Abarghouei, and Toby P. Breckon. "Skip-GANomaly: Skip Connected and Adversarially Trained Encoder-Decoder Anomaly Detection." ArXiv:1901.08954 [Cs], January 25, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1901.08954>.
- [11] Beggel, Laura, Michael Pfeiffer, and Bernd Bischl. "Robust Anomaly Detection in Images Using Adversarial Autoencoders." ArXiv:1901.06355 [Cs, Stat], January 18, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1901.06355>.
- [12] Bergmann, Paul, Michael Fauser, David Sattlegger, and Carsten Steger. "Uninformed Students: Student-Teacher Anomaly Detection with Discriminative Latent Embeddings." ArXiv:1911.02357 [Cs], November 6, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1911.02357>.
- [13] Choi, Hyunsun, Eric Jang, and Alexander A. Alemi. "WAIC, but Why? Generative Ensembles for Robust Anomaly Detection." ArXiv:1810.01392 [Cs, Stat], October 2, 2018. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.01392>.
- [14] Guggilam, Sreelekha, S. M. Arshad Zaidi, Varun Chandola, and Abani Patra. "Bayesian Anomaly Detection Using Extreme Value Theory." ArXiv:1905.12150 [Cs, Stat], May 28, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1905.12150>.
- [15] Maaloe, Lars, Marco Fraccaro, Valentin Loeber, and Ole Winther. "BIVA: A Very Deep Hierarchy of Latent Variables for Generative Modeling." ArXiv:1902.02102 [Cs, Stat], February 6, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1902.02102>.
- [16] Piciarelli, Claudio, Pankaj Mishra, and Gian Luca Foresti. "Image Anomaly Detection with Capsule Networks and Imbalanced Datasets." ArXiv:1909.02755 [Cs], September 6, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1909.02755>.
- [17] Sabokrou, Mohammad, Mohammad Khalooei, Mahmood Fathy, and Ehsan Adeli. "Adversarially Learned One-Class Classifier for Novelty Detection." ArXiv:1802.09088 [Cs], February 25, 2018. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1802.09088>.
- [18] Goldstein, Markus, and Seiichi Uchida. "A Comparative Evaluation of Unsupervised Anomaly Detection Algorithms for Multivariate Data." PLOS ONE 11, no. 4 (April 19, 2016): e0152173. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0152173>.
- [19] Skvara, Vit, Tomas Pevny, and Vaclav Smidl. "Are Generative Deep Models for Novelty Detection Truly Better?" ArXiv:1807.05027 [Cs, Stat], July 13, 2018. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1807.05027>.
- [20] Hendrycks, Dan, and Kevin Gimpel. "A Baseline for Detecting Misclassified and Out-of-Distribution Examples in Neural Networks." ArXiv:1610.02136 [Cs], October 7, 2016. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1610.02136>.
- [21] Mehrtash, Alireza, William M. Wells III, Clare M. Tempany, Purang Abolmaesumi, and Tina Kapur. "Confidence

Calibration and Predictive Uncertainty Estimation for Deep Medical Image Segmentation." ArXiv:1911.13273 [Cs, Eess], November 29, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1911.13273>.

[22] Roady, Ryne, Tyler L. Hayes, Ronald Kemker, Ayesha Gonzales, and Christopher Kanan. "Are Out-of-Distribution Detection Methods Effective on Large-Scale Datasets?" ArXiv:1910.14034 [Cs], October 30, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1910.14034>.

[23] Shafaei, Alireza, Mark Schmidt, and James J. Little. "A Less Biased Evaluation of Out-of-Distribution Sample Detectors." ArXiv:1809.04729 [Cs, Stat], August 20, 2019. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1809.04729>.

[24] Maier-Hein, L., Eisenmann, M., Reinke, A. et al. "Why rankings of biomedical image analysis competitions should be interpreted with care." Nat Commun 9, 5217 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07619-7>

[25] <http://medicalood.dkfz.de/> , [https://www.synapse.org/\(hashtag\)!Synapse:syn21343101/wiki/599515](https://www.synapse.org/(hashtag)!Synapse:syn21343101/wiki/599515)

[26] Zimmerer, D., Paech, D., Lüth, C., Petersen, J., Köhler, G., Maier-Hein, K. (2022). Unsupervised Anomaly Detection in the Wild. In: Maier-Hein, K., Deserno, T.M., Handels, H., Maier, A., Palm, C., Tolxdorff, T. (eds) Bildverarbeitung für die Medizin 2022. Informatik aktuell. Springer Vieweg, Wiesbaden.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-36932-3_6

[27] Zimmerer, David, and Klaus Maier-Hein. "Beyond Heatmaps: A Comparative Analysis of Metrics for Anomaly Localization in Medical Images." International Workshop on Uncertainty for Safe Utilization of Machine Learning in Medical Imaging. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

The MICCAI challenge event is planned for a 2-hr slot.